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Review Article

**DIABETIC FOOT CARE AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE IN
KSA: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**

Dr. Tahani Mohammadali Bakhsh¹, Dr. Hashim Adnan Al Taaha², Dr. Mohammed Fahad Alfahhad², Dr. Mouaiad Abdulrahim Ghabban², Dr. Abdulkarim Omar Abduljawad², Dr. Rayan Saleh Alzahrani³, Dr. Saleh Sadan Alzahrani³, Dr. Mohammed Abdulkhalig Alharbi³, Dr. Ziad Fahad Alalwani³, Dr. Mohammed Saad Alharbi³, Dr. Abdulrahman Fahad Almansour³, Dr. Khalid Ahmed Bakri³, Dr. Hisham Ahmed Alsulami³ and Dr. Ahmed Saleh Alghamdi³

¹ Consultant preventive medicine and public health, Clinical Audit head of Department -Jeddah Health Directorate.

² Service Doctor, MD, KSA.

³ Medical intern, MBBS, KSA.

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Abstract:

Objective: A growing number of research on diabetic foot care knowledge and awareness have been undertaken; nevertheless, there is no clear consensus on the diabetic foot care knowledge and awareness. The goal of this systematic review was to consolidate current data on diabetic foot care knowledge and awareness.

Methods: Authors began with recognizing the important examination proof that spots light on diabetic foot care knowledge and awareness in KSA. Authors led electronic writing look in the accompanying data sets: Ovid Medline (2016 to present), Ovid Medline Daily Update, Ovid Medline in process and other non-filed references, Ovid Embase (2016 to present), The Cochrane Library (latest issue) and Web of Science. Just examinations in English language will be incorporated. The precise selection was acted in close collaboration with a clinical examination curator.

Results: A total of 72 studies were identified in the search, all of them were assessed for eligibility, and 7 articles were included in this review. All included articles targeted diabetic patients and assessed their knowledge and awareness regarding diabetic foot care. Studies were conducted in different regions of KSA as presented in table 1. It is noticed from the table that all studies were cross sectional and data was analyzed using SPSS. Different regions were included and were Riyadh, Alkharj, Aseer, Jazan and Dammam. All studies targeted both type 1 and 2 diabetes except two studies which targeted only type 2 diabetes. Most of included studies reported poor knowledge and practice except for that showed good knowledge and poor attitude.

Conclusion: Study results showed that some studies indicated good knowledge, good practice and poor attitude among participants. On the other hand, other studies reported low knowledge and practice. Furthermore, other authors concluded sufficient knowledge, positive attitude, and lag practice.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Tahani Mohammadali Bakhsh,**

Consultant preventive medicine and public health,

Clinical Audit head of Department -Jeddah Health Directorate.

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INTRODUCTION:

More than 400 million individuals were diagnosed with diabetes in 2014, with the disease disproportionately affecting those over the age of 65. This number is expected to rise by 7.7% by 2030 [1] and 642 million by 2040[2-3]. Sedentary behavior, urbanization, and becoming older are all thought to contribute to this complex condition [4,5]. Diabetes foot is the leading cause of non-traumatic lower limb amputations, affecting half of all diabetic patients [6-8]. Mechanical stress, neuropathy, and angiopathy are key contributors to the development of foot deformities in people with diabetes.

Reduced feeling from sensory neuropathy increases the risk of foot damage, which may cause skin breakdown and foot ulcers [9]. Between 8 and 17 percent of people with diabetes develop foot ulcers every year [10]. Diabetic foot is defined as a foot affected by neurologic abnormalities and varying degrees of peripheral vascular disease due to foot ulceration, infection, or destruction [11]. According to a recent meta-analysis, the prevalence of diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) is highest in men with type 2 diabetes, and the worldwide burden of DFU is estimated to be 6.3% [12]. Native North Americans are said to have the greatest incidence rate in the world. Oceania had a prevalence rate of 3%, Africa 7.2%, Europe 5.1%, Australia 1.5%, and Asia 5.5%. Some nations, notably Canada and Belgium, have a higher reported frequency of [7]. There was 11.6% of DFU in Asia, all of which came from India [7].

According to previous research, the prevalence of DFU in Saudi Arabia ranges from 26% to 61.8%, making it the second most populous nation in the Middle East [13] in terms of diabetic patients [14-15]. It is believed that 5 percent of all fatalities in Saudi Arabia are caused by this complex illness [16]. A majority of diabetes patients with foot issues in Saudi Arabia have foot ulcers, according to data gathered from a registry [17]. It is very uncommon for foot ulcers to be followed by further health issues that make daily living miserable. Furthermore, it raises

healthcare costs since almost 35% of all hospital admissions are due to diabetes-related complications in clinics that specialize in treating the disease [18].

Studies of the cost of treating diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) in the United States and Europe (including nations like France and Belgium) have shown very high direct and indirect costs associated with DFU care [19-22]. Costs associated with treating DFUs in India were estimated to be \$1960 USD in a recent research. The United Arab Emirates (UAE) is experiencing a similar treatment expense burden as other countries and regions due to the rapid increase in the incidence of diabetes mellitus (DM), as shown in [23]. However, with the right prophylactic treatment and preventative measures, diabetic foot problems may be reduced or even eliminated [13]. American Orthopedic Foot and Ankle Society's Diabetes Committee has formulated recommendations for preventative foot care, which include screening, patient education, and treatment [24]. Patients' knowledge and education on early detection and self-management have been shown to be lacking. Concerning, Saudi Arabia has the second-highest rate of DM in the Middle East and the seventh-highest rate in the world. With so little previously published on the Middle East, further study is clearly needed in the region.

METHODS:**Review Question**

This review seeks to evaluate and point out knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA. The specific review questions to be addressed are:

- (1) What is level of diabetic foot care awareness among diabetic patients in KSA?
- (2) What is the knowledge level of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA?

Searches

We began with recognizing the important examination proof that spots light on t knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA. We

led electronic writing look in the accompanying data sets: Ovid Medline (2016 to present), Ovid Medline Daily Update, Ovid Medline in process and other non-filed references, Ovid Embase (2016 to present), The Cochrane Library (latest issue) and Web of Science. Just examinations in English language will be incorporated. The precise selection was acted in close collaboration with a clinical examination curator. Also, the bibliographies of any qualified articles recognized was checked for extra references and reference look were done for all included references utilizing ISI Web of Science.

We considered “published” articles to be compositions that showed up in peer-reviewed journals. Articles present in grey literature were excluded from our review.

Types of studies to be included

We included articles covering how to coordinate different review plans in orderly review of knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA. We did exclude articles only depicting the knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA.

We concentrated on the knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA. We included articles depicting sample sizes and articles that planned to sum up their outcomes to the populace which test was drawn from. Case series and case reports were excluded from our search. Only studies from KSA were considered.

Participants

The systematic review included examinations with tests of diabetic patients.

Searching key words

For every data set, looking through was led by utilizing a mix of the accompanying keywords: (diabetes OR diabetic foot OR diabetes complication OR angiopathy OR neuropathy OR knowledge OR awareness OR foot care OR Kingdom of Saudi Arabia OR systematic review).

We included examinations enrolling members in everyone as well as clinical settings. Studies were incorporated assuming they revealed pr knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA. No comparator or control test size is required in the review to be incorporated.

Studies selection process

All list items were brought into an EndNote record. Two analysts evaluated titles and abstracts for their likely pertinence.

One reviewer freely screened titles and abstracts from the search and any articles that report knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA. We gained the full text of articles that possibly meet the eligibility criteria.

Outcomes

Primary outcome

To determine knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA.

Information extraction¹, (choice and coding)

Information was extracted from the included articles utilizing an electronic information extraction structure on Microsoft Access programming. Two reviewers freely extracted information, utilizing a standard information extraction structure which was created by the survey creators with the end goal of the review. The extraction structure incorporated the accompanying data:

- 1- Publication subtleties: title, authors, journal name and year and city, of distribution, country in which the review was led, sort of distribution, and wellspring of financing.
- 2- Study subtleties: concentrate on plan (cross-sectional, cohort, case-control), settings (clinical or population based), concentrate on transience (planned or review), patients' enlistment techniques (successive or non-continuous), the geographical area, year of information assortment and reaction rate, qualification (consideration and avoidance rules), name of appraisal tool(s), approval of evaluation tool(s).
- 3- Study members' subtleties: number of people reviewed/examined, population qualities including mean age (SD), and gender distribution, relationship status, demographic data.

Data management

A descriptive statistic is employed and relevant data are extracted from eligible studies and presented in tables. We then presented a narrative synthesis of the summary of knowledge and awareness of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in KSA.

RESULTS:

A total of 72 studies were identified in the search, all of them were assessed for eligibility, and 7 articles were included in this review (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Flow chart of selection process

All included articles targeted diabetic patients and assessed their knowledge and awareness regarding diabetic foot care. Studies were conducted in different regions of KSA as presented in table 1. It is noticed from the table that all studies were cross sectional and data was analyzed using SPSS. Different regions were included; Riyadh [25-26, 29], Alkharj [27], Aseer [28], Jazan [30] and Dammam [31]. All studies targeted both type 1 and 2 diabetes except two studies [29-30] which targeted only type 2 diabetes.

Table 1: Methodological characteristics of included studies

Study	Year	Region	Design	Sample size	Sampling	Setting	Diabetes	Analysis	Data collection	Questionnaire
Alshammari [25]	2019	Riyadh	Cross-sectional	368	Random	Diabetic clinic of tertiary care hospital	Type 1 and 2	SPSS 23.0	By investigator	Demographic profile, knowledge (6 items), attitude (7 items), practice (8 items)
AlOwais [26]	2022	Riyadh	Cross-sectional	350	Consecutive	Primary Care Center in Security Forces Hospital	Type 1 and 2	SPSS 22.0	Self-administered	Demographic, knowledge, practice
Shamim [27]	2021	Alkharj	Cross-sectional	224	Convenience	Diabetic clinic, Military Hospital	Type 1 and 2	SPSS 24.0	Face-to-face, Electronic	Demographic, knowledge, attitude, practice
AlJarallah [28]	2020	Aseer	Cross-sectional	351	Convenience	Aseer Central Hospital	Type 1 and 2	SPSS 22.0	Self-administered	Demographic, knowledge, practice
AlOdhayani [29]	2017	Riyadh	Cross-sectional	350	Convenience	Multi-center	Type 2	SPSS 18.0	Self-administered	Demographic, knowledge, awareness, practice
Solan [30]	2016	Jazan	Cross-sectional	250	Random	Jazan Diabetes Center	Type 2	SPSS	Face-to-face	Socioeconomic, information about DM, diabetic foot pattern, knowledge, practice
AlHariri [31]	2017	Dammam	Cross-sectional	229	Random	King Fahd Hospital	Type 1 and 2	SPSS	Self-administered	Demographic, knowledge (16 items), attitude (3 items), practice (10 items)

Most of included studies reported poor knowledge and practice [26-30] except for [25] that showed good knowledge and poor attitude. However, AlHariri [31] reported good knowledge, favorable attitude and good practice. Summary of significant results are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Main results and conclusion of included studies

Study	Male	Female	Knowledge	Attitude	Practice	Factors affecting knowledge, attitude and practice	Conclusion
Alshammari [25]	111	257	76.6%	47.6%	59.8%	Married, Secondary and university education, Employed	Good knowledge, good practice, poor attitude
AlOwais [26]	185	165	65%	-	28%	Gender	Low knowledge and practice
Shamim [27]	131	93	69.2%	70.5%	26.8%	-	Sufficient knowledge, positive attitude, lag practice
AlJarallah [28]	218	133	22.4%	-	29.17%	Female gender, previous education	Low knowledge and practice
AlOdhayani [29]	225	125	Not numerically presented			-	Lack of knowledge, unaware of DM complications, poor practice
Solan [30]	112	138	53.6%	-	68.4%	-	Knowledge and practice are not adequate
AlHariri [31]	134	95	76%	92%	72%	-	Good knowledge, favorable attitude, good practice

There were some factors that affected level of knowledge, attitude and practice either positively or negatively. Figure 2 shows a forest plot of these factors among the total population included in this systematic review.

Figure 2: Forest plot of factors affecting participants knowledge, attitude and practice regarding diabetic foot

DISCUSSION:

From 4.7% in 1980 [32] to 8.4% in 2017 [33], the worldwide adult prevalence of diabetes has grown dramatically. The development of diabetic foot ulcers is a serious consequence of the disease (DFU). Disabling foot ulcers (DFU) are a leading cause of death and hospitalization [34]. DFU occurs in 15%-25% of people with diabetes during the course of their lifetimes [35, 36], and re-ulceration rates are predicted to reach 65% after 5 years. The therapy of DFU may be further complicated by poor wound healing and re-ulceration due to coexisting peripheral artery disease, infection, and neuropathy [36].

Amputation may be necessary if an ulcer does not heal or becomes infected. When combined with diabetes, chronic kidney disease increases the risk of death from amputation to over 70% after seven years [37]. This is true even for those with diabetes who do not have chronic renal disease. In addition, those who lose limbs to DFU have a worse quality of life [38] and are more likely to experience psychological anguish [39]. In addition to having negative effects on the patients themselves, DFUs have been demonstrated to have a negative effect on the quality of life of the carers [40]. Cost estimates range from \$9 to \$13 billion in the United States [41] to £580 million for the National Health Service in the United Kingdom [42]. These figures highlight the enormous clinical and financial challenges caused by DFU. Thus, it is crucial to implement measures to avoid ulcers, and teaching people how to take care of their feet might be one of these measures. The International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot (IWGDF) recommendations state that "education targeted at enhancing foot care knowledge and behavior and encouraging the patient to adhere to this foot care guidance" [43] should be provided to people with diabetes who are at risk of foot ulcers.

Effective foot care education for people with diabetes should provide them with critical, understandable information about their illness, allowing for patients to be active participants in their own treatment and promoting comprehension of how to attain personal health objectives (i.e. self efficacy). If people have faith in their own abilities to take care of their health, they are more likely to take an active role in their own healthcare [44], and this is especially true in the case of diabetes, where self-efficacy is crucial for enhancing self-care behavior [45]. One way to measure a person's self-efficacy is to ask them how confident they are in their ability to engage in the various forms of self-care that have been identified as beneficial for people with diabetes [46].

Patient education alone has not been shown in previous evaluations [47, 48] of clinical outcomes such as ulceration incidence or amputation rates to be an effective strategy of lowering the occurrence of diabetic foot ulceration and amputation. In particular, this paper seeks to evaluate the research in order to comprehend the effect of patient foot care education on diabetics' foot care knowledge, foot self-care behavior, and self-efficacy.

CONCLUSION:

Study results showed that some studies indicated good knowledge, good practice and poor attitude among participants. On the other hand, other studies reported low knowledge and practice. Furthermore, other authors concluded sufficient knowledge, positive attitude, and lag practice.

REFERENCES:

1. Shaw JE, Sicree RA, Zimmet PZ. Global estimates of the prevalence of diabetes for 2010 and 2030. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2010;87:4–14.
2. World Health Organization (WHO) Global Report on Diabetes. Geneva, Switzerland: WHO; 2016.
3. Wild S, Roglic G, Green A, Sicree R, King H. Global prevalence of diabetes: Estimates for the year 2000 and projections for 2030. *Diabetes Care.* 2004;27:1047–53.
4. International Federation of Diabetes (IDF), 2017. About Diabetes [online] Available from: <http://idf.org/about-diabetes/what-is-diabetes> .
5. Global Report on Diabetes. Geneva, Switzerland: WHO; 2017. World Health Organization (WHO).
6. Boulton AJ, Vileikyte L, Ragnarson-Tennvall G, Apelqvist J. The global burden of diabetic foot disease. *Lancet.* 2005;366:1719–24.
7. Zhang P, Lu J, Jing Y, Tang S, Zhu D, Bi Y. Global epidemiology of diabetic foot ulceration: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ann Med.* 2017;49:106–16.
8. Carmona GA, Hoffmeyer P, Herrmann FR, Vaucher J, Tschopp O, Lacraz A, et al. Major lower limb amputations in the elderly observed over ten years: The role of diabetes and peripheral arterial disease. *Diabetes Metab.* 2005;31:449–54.
9. Rahman S. Diabetic Foot Ulcer. Predisposing factors and Management. *BMJ.* 2006;332:407–10.
10. Crawford F, Inkster M, Kleijnen J, Fahey T. Predicting foot ulcers in patients with diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Q J Med.* 2007;100:65–86.
11. Liapis CD, Balzer K, Benedetti-Valentini F, Fernandes e Fernandes J, editors. *Vascular*

- Surgery. Berlin, Heidelberg: European Manual of Medicine Springer; 2007. Diabetic Foot.
12. Veves A, Uccioli L, Manes C, Van Acker K, Komninou H, Philippides P, et al. Comparison of risk factors for foot problems in diabetic patients attending teaching hospitals in four different European states. *Diabet Med*. 1994;11:709–13.
 13. Abdulaziz Al Dawish M, Alwin Robert A, Braham R, Abdallah Al Hayek A, Al Saeed A, Ahmed Ahmed R, et al. Diabetes mellitus in Saudi Arabia: A review of the recent literature. *Curr Diabetes Rev*. 2016;12:359–68.
 14. Al-Hariri M, Al-Enazi A, Alshammari D, Bahamdan A, AL-Khtani S, Al-Abdulwahab A. Descriptive study on the knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding the diabetic foot. *J Taibah Univ Med Sci*. 2017;17:1–5.
 15. Goweda R. Assessment of knowledge and practices of diabetic patients regarding diabetic foot care, in Makkah, Saudi Arabia. *J Fam Med Health Care*. 2017;3:17–22.
 16. World Health Organization – Diabetes Country Profiles. 2016
 17. Abdulghani HM, AlRajeh AS, AlSalman BH, AlTurki LS, AlNajashi NS, Irshad M, et al. Prevalence of diabetic comorbidities and knowledge and practices of foot care among diabetic patients: A cross-sectional study. *Diabetes Metab Syndr Obes*. 2018;11:417–25.
 18. Alshammari ZJ, Alsaid LA, Parameaswari PJ, Alzahrani AA. Attitude and knowledge about foot care among diabetic patients in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2019;8:2089–94.
 19. Ragnarson Tennvall G, Apelqvist J. Health-economic consequences of diabetic foot lesions. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2004;39:132–9.
 20. Prompers L, Huijberts M, Schaper N, Apelqvist J, Bakker K, Edmonds M, et al. Resource utilisation and costs associated with the treatment of DFUs. Prospective data from the Eurodiale Study. *Diabetologia*. 2008;51:1826–34.
 21. Girod I, Valensi P, Laforet C, Moreau-Defarges T, Guillon P, Baron F. An economic evaluation of the cost of DFUs: Results of a retrospective study on 239 patients. *Diabetes Metabol*. 2003;29:269–77.
 22. Van Acker K, Oleen-Burkey M, De Decker L, Vanmaele R, Van Schil P, Matricali G, et al. Cost and resource utilization for prevention and treatment of foot lesions in a diabetic foot clinic in Belgium. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract*. 2000;50:87–95.
 23. Ghosh P, Valia R. Burden of DFUs in India: Evidence Landscape from Published Literature. *Value Health*. 2017;20:9.
 24. Pinzur MS, Slovenkai MP, Trepman E, Shields NN Diabetes Committee of American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society. Guidelines for diabetic foot care: Recommendations endorsed by the Diabetes Committee of the American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society. *Foot Ankle Int*. 2005;26:113–9.
 25. Alshammari ZJ, Alsaid LA, Parameaswari PJ, Alzahrani AA. Attitude and knowledge about foot care among diabetic patients in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*. 2019 Jun;8(6):2089.
 26. AlOwais MM, Shido OA. Knowledge and practice of foot care in patients with diabetes mellitus attending primary care center at Security Forces Hospital, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*. 2020 Dec;9(12):5954.
 27. Shamim M, Alhakbani MS, Alqahtani MS, Alharthi OS, Alhaqbani YJ. Knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding diabetic foot care among Saudi and non-Saudi diabetic patients in Alkharj. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*. 2021 Feb;10(2):859.
 28. Al-Jarallah M, Alqahtani M, Alshahrani S, Alshahrani N, Alshehri AA. Knowledge and practice of diabetic foot care among diabetic patients in Aseer region, Saudi Arabia. *IJMDC*. 2020;4(1):95-100.
 29. Al Odhayani AA, Tayel SA, Al-Madi F. Foot care practices of diabetic patients in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi journal of biological sciences*. 2017 Nov 1;24(7):1667-71.
 30. Solan YM, Kheir HM, Mahfouz MS, Al-Faify AA, Hakami DT, Al Faifi MA, Hakami AW, Hakami AH, Sharif HH. Diabetic foot care: knowledge and practice. *Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*. 2017 Jan 2;6(6):172-7.
 31. Al-Hariri MT, Al-Enazi AS, Alshammari DM, Bahamdan AS, Al-Khtani SM, Al-Abdulwahab AA. Descriptive study on the knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding the diabetic foot. *Journal of Taibah University medical sciences*. 2017 Dec 1;12(6):492-6.
 32. Zhou B, Lu Y, Hajifathalian K, Bentham J, Di Cesare M, Danaei G, Bixby H, Cowan MJ, Ali MK, Taddei C, Lo WC. Worldwide trends in diabetes since 1980: a pooled analysis of 751 population-based studies with 4·4 million participants. *The lancet*. 2016 Apr 9;387(10027):1513-30.

33. Cho NH, Shaw JE, Karuranga S, Huang Y, da Rocha Fernandes JD, Ohlrogge AW, Malanda B. IDF Diabetes Atlas: Global estimates of diabetes prevalence for 2017 and projections for 2045. *Diabetes research and clinical practice*. 2018 Apr 1;138:271-81.
34. Hicks CW, Selvarajah S, Mathioudakis N, Sherman RL, Hines KF, Black III JH, Abularrage CJ. Burden of infected diabetic foot ulcers on hospital admissions and costs. *Annals of vascular surgery*. 2016 May 1;33:149-58.
35. Singh N, Armstrong DG, Lipsky BA. Preventing foot ulcers in patients with diabetes. *Jama*. 2005 Jan 12;293(2):217-28.
36. Armstrong DG, Boulton AJ, Bus SA. Diabetic foot ulcers and their recurrence. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2017 Jun 15;376(24):2367-75.
37. Lavery LA, Hunt NA, Ndiip A, Lavery DC, Van Houtum W, Boulton AJ. Impact of chronic kidney disease on survival after amputation in individuals with diabetes. *Diabetes care*. 2010 Nov 1;33(11):2365-9.
38. Tennvall GR, Apelqvist J. Health-related quality of life in patients with diabetes mellitus and foot ulcers. *Journal of Diabetes and its Complications*. 2000 Sep 1;14(5):235-41.
39. Coffey L, Gallagher P, Horgan O, Desmond D, MacLachlan M. Psychosocial adjustment to diabetes-related lower limb amputation. *Diabetic Medicine*. 2009 Oct;26(10):1063-7.
40. Nabuurs-Franssen MH, Huijberts MS, Nieuwenhuijzen Kruseman AC, Willems J, Schaper NC. Health-related quality of life of diabetic foot ulcer patients and their caregivers. *Diabetologia*. 2005 Sep;48(9):1906-10.
41. Rice JB, Desai U, Cummings AK, Birnbaum HG, Skornicki M, Parsons NB. Burden of diabetic foot ulcers for medicare and private insurers. *Diabetes care*. 2014 Mar 1;37(3):651-8.
42. Kerr M, Rayman G, Jeffcoate WJ. Cost of diabetic foot disease to the National Health Service in England. *Diabetic medicine*. 2014 Dec;31(12):1498-504.
43. Bus S, Van Netten S, Lavery L, Monteiro-Soares M, Rasmussen A, Jubiz Y, Price P. IWGDF guidance on the prevention of foot ulcers in at-risk patients with diabetes. *Diabetes/metabolism research and reviews*. 2016;32(S1):16-24.
44. Bandura A. Self-efficacy: toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological review*. 1977 Mar;84(2):191.
45. Anderson RM, Funnell MM, Butler PM, Arnold MS, Fitzgerald JT, Feste CC. Patient empowerment: results of a randomized controlled trial. *Diabetes care*. 1995 Jul 1;18(7):943-9.
46. Skaff MM, Mullan JT, Fisher L, Chesla CA. A contextual model of control beliefs, behavior, and health: Latino and European Americans with type 2 diabetes. *Psychology and Health*. 2003 Jun 1;18(3):295-312.
47. Hoogveen RC, Dorresteijn JA, Kriegsman DM, Valk GD. Complex interventions for preventing diabetic foot ulceration. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2015(8).
48. Dorresteijn JA, Kriegsman DM, Assendelft WJ, Valk GD. Patient education for preventing diabetic foot ulceration. *Cochrane database of systematic reviews*. 2012(10).